

Synthesis and spectroscopic investigation of heterobimetallic complexes of chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphates

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Abstract : Heterobimetallic complexes of chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphate having formulae $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)[S(S)POCH_2C(CH_3)_2CH\{CH(CH_3)_2\}O].LA$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)[S(S)POCH_2C(CH_3)_2CH_2O].LA$ (LA = $HgCl_2$, $CdCl_2$, CdI_2 , $AgSCN$, $Hg(SCN)_2$, $AgClO_4$, $Hg(ClO_4)_2$, $AgOCOCF_3$, $Hg(OCOCF_3)_2$, $AgOCOCCl_3$, $Hg(OCOCCl_3)_2$) have been prepared by the reaction of chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphate with corresponding Lewis acid in absolute methanol. The products, having 1 : 1 stoichiometry, have been characterized on the basis of analytical and spectral data such as ESI Mass, IR, 1H , ^{13}C , ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn NMR. Heterobimetallic complexes were formed through the coordination of the sulfur atom of chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphates to soft metal acceptors.

Keywords : Alkylene dithiophosphate, heterobimetallic complexes, chlorodiphenyltin(IV).

Introduction

O,O'-Alkylene dithiophosphate occupy a unique position amongst the sulfur and phosphorus containing ligand due to their various possible mode of bonding¹. The interest in organotin dithio derivatives of phosphorus is due to their important industrial²⁻⁴ and agricultural⁵ applications e.g. additive to lubricant oil⁶⁻⁸, insecticides⁹ and pesticides¹⁰. The reactivity of organotin(IV)¹¹ and substituted organotin(IV) O,O'-alkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate¹² with metal acceptors have been reported from our laboratory. In continuation, in the present paper the ligation behavior of $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)[S(S)POGO]$ (G = $-CH_2C(CH_3)CH\{CH(CH_3)_2\}$, $-CH_2-C(CH_3)_2CH_2-$) with Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^I are described.

Experimental

Materials :

$[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)S(S)POCH_2C(CH_3)_2CH_2O]$ was prepared according to reported method¹³. All the solvents were dried and purified by standard procedures¹⁴. The molar conductance of the compounds were measured using a dip type conductivity cell on a desible conductivity meter model DC-610 in DMSO. Estimation of carbon, hydrogen were carried out on Elementar Vario ELIII ana-

lyzer and sulfur was determined by the reported methods¹⁵.

Measurements :

ESI Mass spectra were recorded on a MICROMASS QUARTTO II mass spectrometer. FTIR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu Prestige 21 FTIR Spectrometer (KBr, 4000-400 cm^{-1}). 1H , ^{13}C , ^{31}P , ^{119}Sn NMR spectrum were recorded at 300 MHz, 75.45 MHz, 121.5 MHz and 111.5 MHz respectively on a JEOL AL 300 NMR and EXPNO PROCNO 6534 NMR Spectrometer using TMS (as an Internal standard) for 1H , ^{13}C NMR whereas H_3PO_4 and Me_4Sn (as an External standard) for ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn NMR respectively.

Preparation of chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentane dithiophosphate (1) :

Diphenyltin dichloride (0.343 g, 0.001 mol) and ammonium salt of O,O'-2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentane dithiophosphoric acid (0.257 g, 0.001 mol) in anhydrous benzene was refluxed at room temperature for 3-4 h. After which ammonium chloride was removed by filtration and the product was isolated by stripping off the solvent from the filtrate. The compound was crystallized from pet-ether (60-80 °C). The product was recrystal-

lized with chloroform and dried under vacuo.

The reaction of chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphate with soft metal acceptors :

In a representative experiment, a solution of compound **1** (0.547 g, 0.001 mol) in absolute methanol and Hg(OCOCF₃)₂ (0.426 g, 0.001 mol) in the same solvent were stirred together at room temperature for about 3–4 h. The precipitated product was filtered and washed several times with methanol and finally with diethyl ether. The product was dried over P₂O₅ under vacuo to produce analytically pure product.

Similar heterobimetallic complexes were prepared using HgCl₂, CdI₂, CdCl₂, AgSCN, Hg(SCN)₂, AgClO₄, Hg(ClO₄)₂, Hg(OCOCCL₃)₂, AgOCOCCL₃, AgOCOCF₃, as acceptors with compounds **1** and **2**.

Results and discussion

The reaction of diphenyltin(IV) dichloride with ammonium salt of O,O'-2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentane dithiophosphate in 1 : 1 stoichiometry is carried out in anhydrous benzene to afford white complex.

However, chlorodiphenyltin(IV) O,O'-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-propane dithiophosphates is synthesized by the earlier reported method¹³ which is as follows :

The 1 : 1 heterobimetallic complexes of compounds **1** and **2** with soft Lewis acceptors have been obtained by stirring a mixture of two component in absolute methanol at room temperature

G = -CH₂C(CH₃)₂CH{CH(CH₃)₂}; **LA** = HgCl₂ [**3**], CdCl₂ [**4**], AgSCN [**5**], Hg(SCN)₂ [**6**], AgClO₄ [**7**],

Hg(ClO₄)₂ [**8**], AgOCOCF₃ [**9**], Hg(OCOCF₃)₂ [**10**].

G = -CH₂C(CH₃)₂CH₂-; **LA** = HgCl₂ [**11**], CdI₂ [**12**], Hg(OCOCF₃)₂ [**13**], AgOCOCF₃ [**14**], Hg(OCOCCL₃)₂ [**15**], AgOCOCCL₃ [**16**].

The analytical data of compounds **1** and **2** indicates 1 : 1 [(C₆H₅)₂SnCl : dtp] stoichiometry. The product are white solid, stable at room temperature and are not affected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are soluble in common organic solvent such as CHCl₃, C₆H₆ and CH₃OH.

The analytical data for the heterobimetallic complexes **3-16** given in Tables 1 and 2, corresponds to 1 : 1 (donor : acceptor) stoichiometry. They are solid, stable at room temperature and insoluble in common organic solvent but soluble in DMSO. The molar conductance data of compounds **1**, **2** and their heterobimetallic complexes **3-16** indicate their non-electrolyte nature in DMSO (Tables 1 and 2).

Mass spectra : In ESI Mass spectra of compounds **1** and **2**, the molecular ion peak is observed at *m/z* 547 and *m/z* 506 respectively. The other fragmentation pattern suggested by mass spectra (Compound **1**) are at *m/z* 512 to [M-Cl], 469 to [M(Cl)-CH(CH₃)₂], 392 to [M{(Cl)-(CH(CH₃)₂)}-Ph] and 315 to [M{(Cl)(CH(CH₃)₂)}-2Ph]. The fragmentation pattern are at *m/z* 471 corresponds to [M-Cl], 429 to [M(Cl)-C(CH₃)₂] and 275 to [M{(Cl)(C(CH₃)₂)}-2Ph] (Compound **2**). These data confirm monomeric character and presence of 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the compounds.

In the ESI Mass spectra of heterobimetallic complexes **3** and **15**, the molecular ion peak is observed at *m/z* 817 and *m/z* 1030 respectively. The other fragmentation pattern suggested by mass spectra (Compound **1**) are at *m/z* 782, *m/z* 739, *m/z* 585 and *m/z* 315 corresponds to [M-Cl], [M(Cl)-CH(CH₃)₂], [M{(Cl)(CH(CH₃)₂)}-2Ph], [M{(Cl)(CH(CH₃)₂)}(2Ph)}-HgCl₂]. The fragmentation in Compound **2** are at *m/z* 995, *m/z* 473, *m/z* 387 and *m/z* 186 corresponds to [M-Cl], [M(Cl)-Hg(OCOCCL₃)₂], [M{(Cl)(Hg(OCOCCL₃)₂)}-C(CH₃)₂(CH₂)₂O] and [M{(Cl)(Hg(OCOCCL₃)₂)(C(CH₃)₂(CH₂)₂O)}-2PhPO] respectively.

Table 1. Analytical data of compound **1** and complexes **3-10**

Sr. No.	Compd.	Color	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Elemental analysis		
						C	H	S
1.	1	White	105	85	6.46	43.86 (43.74)	4.78 (4.82)	11.70 (11.74)
2.	3	Yellow	150	76	3.17	29.32 (29.38)	3.19 (3.17)	7.82 (7.86)
3.	4	White	212	68	4.02	30.95 (30.90)	3.37 (3.38)	8.20 (8.24)
4.	5	Grey	157	60	3.40	35.34 (35.38)	3.67 (3.62)	13.48 (13.42)
5.	6	Cream	141(d)	72	4.24	30.56 (30.62)	3.03 (3.04)	14.83 (14.80)
6.	7	White	208	71	4.40	31.81 (31.76)	3.47 (3.43)	8.40 (8.46)
7.	8	Yellow	107(d)	75	3.76	25.36 (25.32)	2.76 (2.78)	6.77 (6.80)
8.	9	White	176	69	4.44	35.77 (35.64)	3.54 (3.53)	8.68 (8.65)
9.	10	Grey	147	58	3.85	27.29 (27.22)	2.70 (2.72)	6.62 (6.68)

Table 2. Analytical data of compound **2** and complexes **11-16**

Sr. No.	Compd.	Color	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Elemental analysis		
						C	H	S
1.	2	White	78	89	6.70	40.43 (40.36)	3.99 (4.01)	12.69 (12.73)
2.	11	White	175	70	3.98	26.37 (26.39)	2.68 (2.70)	8.16 (8.14)
3.	12	White	215	80	4.11	23.48 (23.42)	2.40 (2.41)	7.20 (7.22)
4.	13	Yellow	160	82	3.91	27.12 (27.10)	2.27 (2.28)	6.94 (6.92)
5.	14	Brown	155	76	2.56	31.50 (31.54)	2.66 (2.69)	8.94 (8.99)
6.	15	Yellow	98	74	3.02	24.58 (24.50)	1.90 (1.93)	6.11 (6.14)
7.	16	Brown	240	79	3.88	29.32 (29.26)	2.42 (2.40)	8.36 (8.39)

IR spectra :

FTIR spectra of compounds **1**, **2** and heterobimetallic complexes **3-16** were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} in KBr. Tentative assignments have been made on the basis of earlier report^{12,16}.

In the IR spectra, [$\nu(\text{P})\text{-O-C}$], [$\nu\text{P-O-(C)}$] and [$\nu\text{P=S}$]

bands appear at 1035, 819 and 686 cm^{-1} (Compound **1**) and at 1037, 825 and 702 cm^{-1} respectively (Compound **2**).

The band of medium intensity at $525 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to [$\nu\text{P-S}$] vibration indicates the presence of unidentate O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphate group attached

to the diphenyl moiety (Compounds **1** and **2**). Two weak intensity bands observed at 430 ± 5 and $584 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to Sn-S and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Sn}$ respectively¹².

In the IR spectra of heterobimetallic complexes **3-16**, $[\nu\text{P}=\text{S}]$ absorption invariably shift to lower frequency and appear at 667 ± 9 (Compound **1**) and $677 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Compound **2**). The absorption due to $(\nu\text{P-S})$ remains almost unaffected indicating the presence of unidentate O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphate group. Two absorptions due to $[\nu(\text{P-O-C})]$ and $[\nu\text{P-O-(C)}]$ slightly shifted to higher frequency and appears at 1042 ± 6 , 827 ± 5 (Compound **1**) and 1042 ± 2 , 829 ± 3 (Compound **2**).

The considerable lowering of $(\nu\text{P}=\text{S})$ and increase of $[\nu(\text{P-O-C})]$, $[\nu\text{P-O-(C)}]$ indicate the coordination of both the sulfur atom of the ligand to the tin and soft metal acceptors.

There is a drift of electron density from oxygen and carbon through phosphorus and sulfur to the soft metal atom which increases the bond order of C-O and P-O bonds.

The trichloroacetate group of complexes **15**, **16**, is unidentately coordinated^{17,18}, since the band due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ are located at 1694 ± 8 and 1363 ± 15 respectively with $-\Delta\nu(\text{OCO}) = 331 \pm 7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The trifluoroacetate group of complexes **9**, **10**, is also

unidentate¹⁵, since the band due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ are appeared at 1693 ± 2 and 1433 ± 3 respectively with $-\Delta\nu(\text{OCO}) = 253 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas in complexes **13**, **14**, these bands are appeared at 1691 ± 8 and 1443 ± 9 respectively with $-\Delta\nu(\text{OCO}) = 248 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the complexes **5**, **6**, $\nu(\text{SCN})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\delta(\text{SCN})$ appear at 2088 ± 2 , 729 ± 1 and 468 cm^{-1} respectively indicate presence of S-bonded thiocyanate group¹⁹. In complexes **7**, **8**, the perchlorate group give rise to absorption at 1098 ± 4 and 626 cm^{-1} which are assigned to ν_1 and ν_2 modes of vibration respectively^{20,21}.

The absorption due to Hg-Cl, Cd-Cl and Cd-I stretching mode could not be identified as they lie beyond the recorded range of spectra.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of compounds **1**, **2** and few representative heterobimetallic complexes **6**, **16** are given in Table 3. The position and integration of the peaks are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the complexes. In compounds **1** and **2**, phenyl protons exhibit multiplets at δ 8.01–7.47, however characteristic signals due to OCH_2 , OCH , CH-CH_3 , C-CH_3 are appeared as expected (Table 3).

In the spectra of heterobimetallic complexes **6**, **16**,

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data of compounds **1**, **2** and complexes **6**, **16**

Sr. No.	Compd.	Aryl protons (δ , ppm)	Alkylene protons (δ , ppm)
1.	1	8.00–7.42 (10H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Sn}$)	4.08–4.04 (4H, m, OCH_2), 3.66–3.52 (2H, dd, OCH), $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 12 Hz, $^3J_{\text{P-H}}$ 30 Hz δ 1.92 (1H, m, CH-CH_3), 0.95–0.93 (6H, d, CH-CH_3), $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 6 Hz 0.87–0.85 (6H, d, CH-CH_3), $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 6 Hz 1.11 (6H, s, C-CH_3)
2.	2	7.94–7.46 (10H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Sn}$)	3.73–3.67 (4H, d, OCH_2), $^3J_{\text{P-H}}$ 18 Hz 0.87 (6H, s, CH_3)
3.	6	8.01–7.47 (10H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Sn}$)	4.11–4.02 (4H, m, OCH_2) 3.83–3.69 (2H, dd, OCH), $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 12 Hz, $^3J_{\text{P-H}}$ 30 Hz δ 2.00 (1H, m, CH-CH_3), 1.00–0.98 (6H, d, CH-CH_3), $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 6 Hz 0.94–0.92 (6H, d, CH-CH_3), $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 6 Hz 1.18 (6H, s, C-CH_3)
4.	16	8.01–7.47 (10H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Sn}$)	3.80–3.70 (4H, d, OCH_2), $^3J_{\text{P-H}}$ 15 Hz 0.91 (6H, s, CH_3)

C₆H₅-Sn signals remains almost unaffected whereas there is slight low field shifting in OCH₂, OCH, CH-CH₃, C-CH₃ protons. The low field shift in alkyl proton indicates considerable shift of electron density from oxygen to the soft metal acceptors through sulfur which favour the presence of bridging ligands^{22,23} and support the results obtained from IR spectral data.

³¹P NMR spectra :

In the ³¹P NMR spectra of compound **1** and **2**, a single peak is observed at δ 88.23 and δ 97.06 ppm respectively which is in agreement with the earlier report for a four coordinated tin atom in dithiophosphate derivatives²⁴.

The ³¹P NMR spectra of representative heterobimetallic complexes **3** and **11** show deshielding of the phosphorus atom to the extent of about δ 14–21 ppm from the parent compounds **1**, **2** (Table 4). The deshielding of phosphorus atom in heterobimetallic complexes supports the re-

sults from IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

¹³C NMR spectra :

In ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectra of compounds **1**, **2** and representative complexes **3**, **11**, signals due to phenyl carbons, CH₃-C, CH₃-CH, CH-OCH, OCH₂, OCH and C_{ipso} are found as expected (Table 4). The significant deshielding of the carbons in heterobimetallic complexes **3**, **11** authenticate results obtained from IR, ¹H and ³¹P NMR spectra.

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

In ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of compounds **1** and **2**, a single peak is observed at δ 206.92 and δ 178.67 ppm respectively which correspond to a four coordinated tetrahedral tin atom²⁴. In ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of complexes **3** and **11**, tin atom are found to be deshielded than parent compounds and a peak is observed at δ 178.24 and δ 122.80 ppm respectively (Table 4). It is concluded that on co-

Table 4. ¹³C, ³¹P, ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectral data of compounds **1**, **2** and complexes **3**, **11**

Sr. No.	Compd.	¹³ C (δ, ppm)	³¹ P (δ, ppm)	¹¹⁹ Sn (δ, ppm)
1.	1	Ar-C (C _{ipso} -Sn) 141.30, (o to Sn) 135.59, (m to Sn) 129.06, (p to Sn) 130.62 CH ₃ -C (18.66), CH ₃ -CH (22.12), CH-OCH (29.25), C-C _{ipso} (36.41), OCH ₂ (79.81), ² J _{C-P} 33 Hz OCH (92.31), ² J _{C-P} 39 Hz	88.23	-206.92
2.	2	Ar-C (C _{ipso} -Sn) 150.20, (o to Sn) 134.73, (m to Sn) 128.08, (p to Sn) 128.81 OCH ₂ (73.14), ² J _{C-P} 32 Hz CH ₃ (21.84), C-C _{ipso} (31.84)	97.06, ² J _{P-C} 39 Hz, ² J _{P-Sn} 75 Hz	-178.67
3.	3	Ar-C (C _{ipso} -Sn) 151.43, (o to Sn) 136.22, (m to Sn) 128.79, (p to Sn) 131.22 CH ₃ -C (18.73), CH ₃ -CH (22.19), CH-OCH (28.88), C-C _{ipso} (36.43), OCH ₂ (79.88), ² J _{C-P} 36 Hz OCH (91.69), ² J _{C-P} 39 Hz	110.04	-178.60
4.	11	Ar-C (o to Sn) 136.81, (m to Sn) 128.38, (p to Sn) 127.94 OCH ₂ (76.45), ² J _{C-P} 33 Hz CH ₃ (20.89), C-C _{ipso} (32.04)	111.59, ² J _{P-C} 36 Hz, ² J _{P-Sn} 74 Hz	-122.80

ordination from the sulfur to soft metal acceptor, the shift of electron density from the diphenyltin group deshielded the tin atom.

On the basis of analytical and spectral (ESI Mass, IR, ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn NMR) evidences, a tetrahedral¹² structure (Fig. 1) has been assigned to compounds **1-2**, however in the case of heterobimetallic complexes **3-16**, it is assumed that two molecules of metal acceptors are bind to two different sulfur atom. The dithio group thus act as a bridge between chlorodiphenyltin and soft metal¹² (Fig. 2). The proposed structures may be as follows :

Fig. 1. The proposed structure of compounds **1** and **2**.

Fig. 2. The proposed structure of heterobimetallic complexes **3-16**.

In these heterobimetallic complexes, Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} are tricoordinated²⁵⁻²⁷, while Ag^{I} possess a coordination number of 2^{12,28}.

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